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The value of nature and valuation instruments in EU policy and beyond

An ethical analysis of common nature valuation instruments

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List of acronyms

- **CAP** Common Agricultural Policy
- **CBA** Cost-benefit analysis
- **CSRD** Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive
- **CV** Contingent valuation
- **DCE** Discrete choice experiment
- **EGE** European Group on Ethics in Science and New Technologies
- **EIB** European Investment Bank
- **ELP** Environmental Legal Personhood
- **EPIC** Environmental Policies and Individual Behaviour Change
- **ERR** Economic rate of return
- **ESRS** European Sustainability Reporting Standards
- **FONAFIFO** Fondo Nacional de Financiamiento Forestal
- **INCA** Integrated System for Natural Capital Accounting
- **IPBES** Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services
- **IUCN** International Union for Conservation of Nature
- **JRC** Joint Research Centre
- **MAES** Mapping and Assessment of Ecosystems and Services
- **MAMCA** Multi-actor multi-criteria analysis
- **MCA** Multi-criteria analysis

- **MCDA** Multi-criteria decision analysis
- **NCA** Natural capital accounting
- **NCAVES** Natural capital accounting and valuation of ecosystem services
- **OECD** Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
- **PES** Payments for ecosystem services
- **PINE** Policy Instruments for the Environment
- **REDD+** Reducing Emissions from Deforestation and Forest Degradation
- **RoN** Rights of Nature
- **SAEGE** Support for the Activities of the European Group on Ethics (EGE) by European Academia and Ethics Bodies
- **SDG** Sustainable Development Goal
- **SEEA** System of Environmental-Economic Accounting
- **SEEA-EA** SEEA Ecosystem Accounting
- **SFDR** Sustainable Finance Disclosure Regulation
- **SOCRATES** Social Multi-Criteria Assessment of European Policies
- **TCM** Travel cost method
- **WAVES** Wealth Accounting and Valuation of Ecosystem Services
- **WTA** Willingness to accept
- **WTP** Willingness to pay

Executive summary

This report provides a practice-oriented overview of how widely used valuation instruments — cost–benefit analysis (CBA), multi-criteria analysis (MCA), natural capital accounting (NCA), stated-preference methods (including contingent valuation and choice experiments), revealed-preference methods (including hedonic pricing and the travel cost method), payments for ecosystem services (PES), nature and biodiversity credits, and the rights of nature (RoN; included here as a qualitative valuation and governance approach) — are currently applied in environmental policymaking in the EU and international contexts. It provides an ethical reflection on these instruments, and in particular assesses how they capture different values of nature. While these instruments are often presented as technical tools, their use raises fundamental ethical questions about which values of nature are captured, which are marginalised, and whether some values should resist quantification or trade-offs altogether.

The report introduces an analytical framework based on three types of value of nature – instrumental, intrinsic and relational – to structure the overview of valuation instruments and to make explicit the ethical assumptions and trade-offs embedded in commonly used valuation practices. It then compares instruments along recurring questions concerning what is valued, how value is represented and aggregated, which values are prioritised, and what tends to fall outside the scope of appraisal. These findings are summarised in a table, and a full analysis per instrument is provided in Annex 1.

The main findings are as follows:

- No single valuation instrument dominates environmental policymaking; instruments are applied selectively across policy contexts.
- Valuation instruments are not value-neutral but embed distinct assumptions about the value of nature and human–nature relationships, assumptions that shape policy outcomes. Policy outcomes are further

shaped by how instruments are combined and situated within governance practices, including participation, oversight, and institutional context.

- Prevailing instruments are market-based ones that predominantly prioritise instrumental values of nature by translating ecological processes into measurable contributions to human welfare or economic activity, thereby overlooking intrinsic and relational values.
- Even when broader values are acknowledged in principle, instruments frequently privilege what can be quantified, priced, or traded, reinforcing a logic that may conflict with ethical perspectives that treat certain ecological entities or relationships as non-substitutable or morally non-tradeable, potentially allowing for continued negative environmental impacts to be compensated (by various mechanisms), and often simplifying ecological and social complexity.
- Rights of Nature frameworks articulate an intrinsic value of nature by recognising nature as a rights-bearing entity rather than a resource. These frameworks remain largely absent in EU policy.
- A growing trend towards system-level thinking seeks to integrate ecological considerations into economic governance structures, though often without fundamentally shifting underlying instrumental framings of nature.
- Individual instruments are seen to be insufficient to deliver effective environmental policy across contexts; as a result, in practice instruments are sometimes combined to better align plural value perspectives with policymaking needs and help avoid systematic exclusion of relational or intrinsic values of nature.
- The effectiveness of valuation instruments depends on their design, data quality, and context. Ongoing review helps uncover unintended effects like problematic incentives, unequal impacts, or ecological oversimplification.

Introduction

This report was prepared by the project Support for the Activities of the European Group on Ethics (EGE) by European Academia and Ethics Bodies (SAEGE) in February 2026 in response to a request from the Secretariat of the EGE in the context of the EGE's forthcoming Opinion on the value of nature. It forms one of two reports supporting the EGE's reflection.

The European Commission requested advice from the EGE on approaches to valuing nature in governance and across society, particularly in relation to the ethical questions that emerge from how humans relate to nature and their responsibility towards it. The questions posed by the European Commission to the EGE were as follows:

- Which assumptions about the value of nature, biodiversity, ecosystems and of the relationship of humans to nature should underpin policy decisions? How are these dimensions integrated into (economic) policymaking at EU and national levels, and in underlying models used for impact assessment, policy design, monitoring and evaluation? On this basis, what kinds of governance action are required, also with regard to the further development of the European Green Deal and of what is to follow it, and the EU's strategies and actions in the global context?
- What are important ethical considerations as regards conceptualisations about the rights and standing of non-human parts of nature? Who is best placed to invoke, enshrine, and adjudicate these rights — and on what basis?

- How are approaches that value nature, and human actions with effect on nature, in economic terms to be assessed from an ethical perspective? What are important ethical perspectives as regards socio-economic systems and the need for a global transition to sustainability?

Different valuation approaches rest on distinct assumptions about the value of nature. A range of valuation instruments are already used in policy. However, the ethical assumptions and trade-offs associated with the use of these instruments are not always made explicit. This report therefore looks at how widely used valuation instruments function in practice, what kinds of values they emphasise or exclude, and which concerns tend to fall outside their scope.

Methods

This report is based on an exploratory desk review of selected valuation instruments as applied in EU and international policy contexts. The review was based on structured online searches, restricted to the institutional domains of leading EU and international public bodies (e.g. OECD, World Bank, UN, European Commission), to identify authoritative policy guidance, appraisal manuals, technical documentation, and documented applications of valuation instruments.

Search strings were developed per instrument and are listed in Annex 2. Document selection was guided by the following criteria: (1) authorship or commissioning by recognised public or intergovernmental bodies; (2) relevance to domains where valuation instruments are applied; and (3) publication within the past decade. Additional searches were conducted to complement the initial screening and to substantiate selected case studies and valuation considerations. These included relevant academic publications and older policy or technical documents where needed.

Following document selection, the material was analysed through a structured comparative reading. The analysis was guided by a set of recurring analytical dimensions. These included (1) what is being valued; (2) whether and how instrumental values are framed in terms of use and non-use; (3) how value is represented (monetary, biophysical, qualitative, or legal); (4) assumptions about commensurability; (5) how values are compared or aggregated; (6) the implied human-nature ontology; (7) what tends to fall outside the scope of the instrument; and (8) how non-monetisable values are handled in practice.

The approach taken herein has several limitations. The review was not systematic and cannot claim comprehensive coverage of all applications of the instruments discussed or of instruments used less widely. The reliance on domain-restricted searches may have excluded relevant materials not taken up by major policymaking bodies and international institutions. The report also focuses on a limited number of illustrative examples.

Introduction to valuation instruments

Building on the IPBES understanding of policy instruments as tools used by decision-makers to influence behaviour and achieve policy objectives (Mangalagu et al., 2024, p. 276), this report focuses on a subset of instruments that are relevant for the valuation of nature in the EU or are employed frequently at the international level.

Cost–benefit analysis (CBA), stated- and revealed-preference methods, and multi-criteria analysis (MCA) are widely documented in OECD (2002) and European Commission (2023, Chapter 8) guidance as standard methods for comparing policy options and assessing trade-offs. Natural capital accounting (NCA), as operationalised through the United Nations (n.d.) System of Environmental–Economic Accounting (SEEA), links ecological change to macro-economic reporting. Instruments such as payments for ecosystem services (PES) — recognised in EU policy guidance (European Union, 2021b) — and nature or biodiversity credits — as promoted within the EU *Roadmap toward Nature Credits* (European Commission, 2025a) — reflect the growing use of incentive-based and market-oriented mechanisms to mobilise finance for conservation.

There is no settled definition of what constitutes a valuation instrument in relation to nature. The inclusion of Rights of Nature (RoN) in this report, although not yet broadly considered a valuation instrument in policy practice, recognises that valuation may not operate solely through appraisal- or incentive-based approaches: drawing on the IPBES typology of policy instruments (Mangalagu et al., 2024, p. 276) and the IPBES (2022, p. 39) *Assessment Report on the Diverse Values and Valuation of Nature*, rights-based

instruments represent a distinct governance approach in which nature’s value is articulated through legal standing and rights rather than commensurable economic measures.

The sub-sections below describe each valuation instrument in brief.

Cost–benefit analysis (CBA)

Cost–benefit analysis (CBA) is a decision-making framework that compares and ranks options according to their net effect on overall social welfare. It seeks, as far as possible, to express all significant benefits and costs for society in monetary terms, covering economic, social, and environmental impacts (European Commission, 2021a, p. 20). It does so by monetising relevant costs and benefits and aggregating them into a single, comparable metric. In practice, CBA has become a central decision-making tool in infrastructure appraisal and regulatory impact assessment: it structures the comparison of alternatives, informs the selection of preferred options, and provides an evidence-based justification for approving or rejecting policies based on their expected net benefits.

Multi-criteria analysis (MCA)

Environmental decision-making often requires accounting for ecological, social, and economic aspects, i.e., the three pillars of integrated valuation (Liquete et al., 2016). One of the possible methodologies to support this kind of multi-dimensional assessment is multi-criteria analysis (MCA). MCA and multi-criteria decision analysis (MCDA) describe structured approaches to support decision-making by systematically exploring different, and often conflicting, perspectives and options and weighing them against multiple criteria. Deliberative methods, such as stakeholder deliberation and other participatory methods, are central to MCA. MCA asks different stakeholders to indicate which criteria matter most to them and translates these preferences into weights that influence the overall scoring, ensuring the final evaluation reflects a range of viewpoints rather than a single perspective. MCDA is especially valuable when it is impractical or undesirable to simplify a multi-objective problem into a single objective, particularly in participatory contexts where diverse stakeholders pursue different goals (Linkov et al., 2006).

Natural capital accounting (NCA)

As one United Nations (n.d., p. 1) background paper notes, there is a growing recognition that “[t]he calculations that guide crucial decisions must be changed so that nature and its benefits appear on the ledger.” NCA addresses this by combining biophysical and, where appropriate, monetary measures to track natural capital stocks and flows and their contribution to economic activity and societal well-being (World Bank, 2023). Conceptually, NCA functions as a statistical accounting framework rather than a valuation method in its own right. In practice, NCA informs land-use planning, national reporting, climate and biodiversity policy, and “beyond GDP” (Joint Research Centre, 2024) assessments. It structures information on ecosystem extent, environmental conditions, and service flows in ways that are compatible with national

economic accounts and can therefore inform or feed into other valuation approaches, such as PES (Bass et al., 2017).

Revealed-preference methods

Revealed-preference methods work by deriving the implicit value of an environmental good from people’s behaviour in related markets rather than by asking them directly (European Commission, 2023, p. 519). Two main variants are used. The hedonic pricing method calculates the price premium (or discount) embedded in property or rental prices that can be attributed to specific environmental characteristics — such as cleaner air, access to parks, or lower noise levels — and is frequently applied to assess the amenity value of environmental quality in particular locations (United Nations Statistical Commission, 2021, pp. 194–200). In practice, this involves comparing otherwise similar properties and isolating how differences in environmental conditions are reflected in prices. The travel cost method (TCM), by contrast, pinpoints the value of recreational areas by analysing how many trips people take to a site and how much time and money they spend getting there (United Nations Statistical Commission, 2021, pp. 195–200). The effort and expense incurred in travelling to a forest, park, or protected area then provides an indirect indication of how much visitors value the experience.

Stated-preference methods

Stated-preference methods estimate monetary values for environmental changes that do not have market prices, often by using specially designed surveys to elicit people’s willingness to pay (WTP) or willingness to accept (WTA) or by asking them to choose between hypothetical scenarios. They have been used to elicit non-use information across domains, including “cultural, environmental, health, and transportation goods and services” (Watson, 2021,

p. 15). Two core variants are contingent valuation (CV), which asks for WTP/WTA directly, and choice modelling, which infers values from repeated choices among alternatives with different attributes and costs (European Commission, 2023, p. 519).

Payments for ecosystem services (PES)

The United Nations Economic Commission for Europe (UNECE, n.d.) notes that the term 'ecosystem services' is characterized by the benefit for humans, in contrast to the intrinsic value of nature. PES schemes provide financial incentives to landowners or resource managers in exchange for the voluntary delivery of specific ecosystem services or conservation actions, such as carbon sequestration, water regulation, or habitat protection. In the literature and policy practice, PES is understood broadly, ranging from narrowly defined market-like arrangements involving direct transactions between service providers and beneficiaries to wider schemes in which those who benefit from ecosystem services contribute indirectly, e.g., via taxes or public funds, to those who manage and supply them (e.g., Cavelier and Munro Gray, 2012, p. 3). In policy settings, PES often acts as an implementation instrument in land-use and resource management.

Nature and biodiversity credits

Globally, the economic and social costs associated with nature loss are high and increasing. Although societal actors, like private economic actors, may recognise their exposure to biodiversity-related risks, they often lack the awareness or sufficient incentives to invest in systemic solutions and address root causes. "Nature markets," i.e., market-based mechanisms using tradable instruments linked to positive outcomes for nature, aim at creating financial

incentives by issuing credits that channel finance toward activities supporting nature conservation (Fiore and Grabbe, 2025). Nature or biodiversity credits are tradable certificates representing verified, measurable, and lasting positive outcomes for nature (Biodiversity Credit Alliance, 2024). Biodiversity credits are a key subset, reflecting biodiversity's central role in ecosystem resilience. These credits translate ecological improvements, such as habitat restoration or species gains, into standardised units that can mobilise private finance or sometimes offset impacts, effectively linking financial incentives to measurable environmental outcomes (World Economic Forum, 2022). In practice, they function as a financing and compliance tool in restoration policy and corporate sustainability strategies. Unlike carbon credits, which focus on CO₂ emissions, nature and biodiversity credits cover a broader range of ecological factors.

Rights of Nature (RoN)

RoN is a legal and judicial theory according to which natural elements, and more generally the environment, have inherent rights, with legal standing and enforceable protections similar to those found in human rights law. Building on the work of Stone (1972) in the article "Should Trees Have Standing?", lawyers and legal scholars around the world have worked to embed RoN within legal systems. Within RoN, nature is treated as a non-human rights holder, encompassing both living and non-living elements of the natural world. RoN encompasses the idea that the whole biosphere, meant as the place in which life can exist, is endowed with natural rights, including the right to exist, thrive, and regenerate (Kauffman and Martin, 2021). Most RoN initiatives are designed to function as constitutional amendments or through civil law mechanisms. Complementing these approaches, the concept of ecocide offers a means to address violations of nature's rights by tackling environmental harm through criminal law.

Analytical framework

Valuation instruments used in policymaking reflect assumptions about what is considered valuable, how value is represented, and how trade-offs are addressed in decision-making. As noted in the value theory literature (e.g., Hirose and Olson, 2015, p. 10), valuation repeatedly raises questions, e.g., about measurement, comparison, and aggregation of different kinds of value. This section outlines these questions and structures a subsequent comparative overview of widely used nature valuation instruments (see Table 1).

The tripartite value typology

How does the ethical literature conceptualize the different types of value of nature that these instruments capture? Following Christie et al. (2021; see also Chan et al. 2016), the three value types distinguished here are instrumental, intrinsic, and relational values. These form the basis of the ethical reflection on the different nature valuation instruments.

Instrumental values

Instrumental values frame nature as a means to human ends, through ecosystem services or nature's contributions to human well-being. In this type of valuing, nature matters not in itself, but insofar as it provides usefulness or utility to humans, for instance, by supporting communities' economic well-being or subsistence, by satisfying human needs, preferences, interests, or desires, or by serving as a resource, asset, capital, or property for the delivery of ecosystem services (Chan et al., 2016; Lau et al., 2019; Bonnett, 2012). This instrumental provision of utility may also extend to legal matters, since recognizing the right to a clean environment as a social right (as embedded in

many constitutions), is also an instrumental framing of nature (Jung et al., 2014).

Different conceptualizations often overlap in the ethical literature. Because instrumental values refer to a means to an end, they are in principle substitutable, meaning that it is acceptable to consider equivalents that provide similar benefits, although it might not always be feasible in practice to achieve or establish these equivalents (Schröter et al., 2020). Although conceptually not necessarily linked, anthropocentric values are often associated with instrumental values because anthropocentrism is defined as human-centred, and nature's value is entirely derivative within this framework, flowing from human valuation.

Within instrumental values, environmental economic scholarship further draws a distinction between use and non-use values (Aruga, 2022). Use values arise from actual or potential interactions with nature, either directly (e.g., food, timber, medicinal resources) or indirectly through ecological functions that support human well-being (e.g., water regulation, flood control, pollination). Non-use values, by contrast, are conceptualised by Aruga as not depending on any direct interaction or utilisation: they may include existence value (valuing nature because humans care that nature exists), bequest value (valuing the preservation of nature for future generations), and stewardship value (valuing nature out of a sense of care, responsibility, or moral obligation).

The Total Economic Value framework, a framework often discussed in environmental economics, also splits the value of environmental assets into use values and non-use values, and lists existence value, bequest value, and altruistic value (valuing that others have access to nature's benefits).

However, it can be argued that non-use values cannot easily be accommodated within the classification of instrumental values, and that they overlap with relational values. For instance, stewardship is not adequately described as the utility humans derive from caring for nature; it refers instead to a felt responsibility toward particular places and beings, rooted in ongoing relationships rather than individual preferences, making an instrumental valuation that allows for trade-offs more difficult (Chan et al., 2016). Similarly, bequest value — while framed instrumentally as intergenerational preference satisfaction — can express a relational commitment to future generations and to the continuity of human–nature relationships that exceeds what preference-based aggregation can capture. However, while non-use value is not a standard category within ethical literature, it is included in the analytical table below given its widespread use in environmental economic frameworks.

Intrinsic values

In contrast to instrumental valuation, in an intrinsic framing, nature is valuable independent of serving human needs and of how it relates to humans. This framing does not imply that nature cannot have a valuable relation to humans, but rather that nature is valued independently of that relationship (Himes and Muraca, 2018). In this framing, natural entities are inherently morally valuable, and non-human beings have their own interests or needs that warrant moral consideration in their own right (Rolston, 1994; Callicot, 1995).

In the IPBES conceptual framework, intrinsic values are equated with non-anthropocentric values (Pascual et al., 2017), but this can be challenged by arguing that humans can genuinely value nature for its own sake, for instance through aesthetic and cultural appreciation, without this collapsing into mere instrumentalism (Hargrove 1992). However, by referring to nature as valuable in itself, as an end rather than a means, intrinsic values arguably conflict with instrumental values because they cannot be traded off against aggregate usefulness. That is, intrinsic valuation imposes moral constraints: a natural entity with moral value cannot simply be weighed against competing interests.

Intrinsic values are both non-substitutable and incommensurable in a strong sense: a natural entity that is morally valuable cannot be replaced by another entity delivering equivalent ecological functions, nor can its value be expressed on the same scale as human welfare benefits or economic outputs without reducing a moral status to a preference, effectively negating the intrinsic value.

Relational values

Whereas instrumental values locate value in outcomes and intrinsic values in the object itself, relational values locate value in relationships. Relational values refer to the values of, or emerge from, meaningful, desirable, just, and reciprocal relationships of humans with nature and among humans through nature (Chan et al., 2016; Schröter et al., 2020). These include the non-substitutable meanings, responsibilities, and attachments that humans hold in relation to particular natural entities and non-human beings (Christie et al., 2021, p. 6; Chan, Gould and Pascual, 2018). As relational values are context-dependent, often place-based, and non-tradeable, they are regarded largely non-substitutable (Kenter et al., 2019).

While ethical scholarship sees a clearer difference between instrumental and intrinsic values, relational values and instrumental or intrinsic values arguably show more overlap. First, the boundary between instrumental and relational values is conceptually blurry precisely because most instrumental relationships with nature are also, at some level, relational ones. Riechers et al. (2025) show how human-nature relationships in practice exhibit the fluidity of relational and instrumental values. However, Chan et al. (2016) insist that the presence of usefulness does not disqualify a value from being relational; what matters is whether the relationship itself is part of what is valued. Himes and Muraca (2018) reinforce this by defining relational values as anthropocentric yet non-instrumental: they involve humans in the relationships valued, but the value cannot be reduced to utility. Second, intrinsic and relational values also overlap in ways that the standard typology of the three values does not imply. Plumwood (2005) argues that recognising the intrinsic value of nature requires

a relational selfhood — a view on humans as constituted through, rather than merely adjacent to, relationships with the natural world. In this view, intrinsic value claims are not made from a position of detachment but emerge from deep relational engagement. Similarly, Rolston (1994) acknowledges that although intrinsic value and relational value are conceptually distinct, they are not fully separable in practice, as the recognition and activation of value depend on human perception. However, although relational valuing encompasses elements of both intrinsic and instrumental valuing, scholars argue that it remains ethically meaningful as a distinct concept (e.g., Deplazes-Zemp & Chapman, 2021).

Relationships between the value types

The terms ‘non-substitutability’ and ‘incommensurability’ are key in the conceptualizations of the three different value types. They are related but distinct. Where values are incommensurable — meaning they cannot be measured on a single common scale or traded off against one another without distortion — the entities that bear those values also cannot be substituted, because no equivalent can be found that preserves what made the original valuable in the first place (O'Neill, Holland and Light, 2008). It is worth noting that incommensurability can be understood in both a substantive sense — where no common measure between value types exists in principle — and an epistemic sense — where such a measure may exist but cannot be constructed or accessed given our cognitive and practical limitations. The non-substitutability of intrinsic values rests on the stronger, substantive claim, while the non-substitutability of relational values may be better characterized as epistemic, reflecting the practical impossibility of capturing particular, place-based meanings in standardized metrics rather than a metaphysical barrier to comparison.

The three value types introduced in this section — instrumental, intrinsic, relational — are thus not clearly demarcated, nor mutually exclusive, but show overlaps in conceptualizations. Himes et al. (2024) show how this reflects the

importance of context and diverse knowledge systems. Ultimately, how nature is valued — whether through instrumental, intrinsic, or relational framings, or through combinations and tensions among them — cannot be understood independently of the place, culture, and ontological commitments in which valuation is embedded. Different knowledge systems may not map neatly onto the three categories discussed here. Recognising this context-dependence is relevant for understanding how nature valuation works in practice.

Nevertheless, Himes et al. argue that maintaining a working distinction between instrumental and relational domains remains important for effective environmental policy implementation. This capacity for distinction may equally matter for ethical reflection on relevant policy options. For instance, although some scholars question whether relational values add anything conceptually beyond intrinsic and instrumental values (e.g., Baard 2025), this value type nonetheless remains central in policy debates. Relational values feature prominently in discussions on ecosystem services (Stålhammar & Thorén, 2019, p. 1201) and are adopted by the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services (Pascual et al., 2017). Hence, while acknowledging its conceptual limitations and challenges, this report will continue to build on the tripartite value typology of instrumental, intrinsic and relational values for the purpose of conducting an ethical reflection on environmental policy and nature valuation instruments in particular.

Comparative overview of valuation instruments

The following analytical framework outlines these questions and structures a subsequent comparative overview of widely used instruments in the valuation of nature.

The following recurring questions are applied across subsections to support the comparison of instruments:

- **What is being valued?** Instrumental values, intrinsic values, or relational values?
- **Instrumental value: use vs non-use?** Within instrumental values, a further distinction can be made between use and non-use values.
- **How is value represented?** Values of nature can be represented in different ways in policy and decision-making. Quantitative (monetary) representation expresses value in monetary terms, such as prices or monetary accounts of ecosystem services. These monetary approaches do not merely measure value in a neutral or technical way; rather, they carry implicit value judgements about what matters, how it matters, and how trade-offs should be handled. Quantitative (non-monetary or biophysical) representation uses measurable indicators such as hectares of habitat, species abundance, or ecosystem condition indices, while qualitative representation conveys value through narratives, deliberation, legal principles, cultural interpretations, or ethical arguments rather than numerical metrics (e.g., Busch et al., 2012).
- **Assumption about commensurability?** How are values compared and/or aggregated? While many valuation approaches aggregate impacts into comparable units (often monetary), others emphasise values of nature that are plural, non-substitutable, or not readily aggregated. The IPBES (2022, p. 48) highlights tensions arising from how valuation indicators are compared and combined in decision-making. Differences in commensurability and aggregation may affect what kinds of values instruments can capture and bring into decision-making.
- **Implied human–nature ontology?** Valuation instruments implicitly portray both what nature is and how humans relate to it, for example, as a resource to be used, capital to be managed, or a rights-bearing subject. These underlying assumptions about the human–nature

relationship may shape how value, responsibility, and limits are handled in decision-making processes.

- **What tends to fall outside the scope of valuation?** According to an IPBES (2022, p. 16) assessment report, choosing appropriate methods “requires assessing trade-offs between their relevance, robustness and resource requirements”: no single valuation instrument can currently capture all relevant values or decision-making needs. Making explicit what falls outside the scope of these instruments helps clarify their limits when applied in policy settings.
- **Non-monetisable values?** Are non-monetisable values captured or excluded within the nature valuation instruments?

For the sake of brevity, Table 1 (overleaf) provides an overview of how the selected instruments differ across the questions introduced above:

- Columns are ordered from instrumental, behaviour-based-, or welfare-based valuation toward recognition of relational, intrinsic, and non-commensurable values of nature.
- Rows are ordered from foundational value assumptions to operational and practical implications.

Each column corresponds to a valuation instrument detailed in Annex 1, which develops the considerations summarised in the table in greater detail. The annex situates the instruments with respect to different value assumptions and trends and provides references to key policy documents and illustrative case material. Full analyses can be accessed by clicking on the hyperlinked instrument titles.

Table 1. Overview of valuation instruments

Recurring questions	<u>Revealed-preference</u>	<u>Cost-benefit analysis (CBA)</u>	<u>Stated-preference methods</u>	<u>Natural capital accounting (NCA)</u>	<u>Payments for ecosystem services (PES)</u>	<u>Nature and biodiversity credits</u>	<u>Multi-criteria analysis (MCA)</u>	<u>Rights of Nature</u>
What is being valued?	Instrumental use value (market behaviour)	Instrumental value (aggregate human welfare)	Instrumental value (expressed preferences including non-use)	System-level instrumental value (ecosystems as capital)	Instrumental value (standardised biodiversity gains)	Instrumental, relational values in stewardship framed contractually (ecosystem service delivery)	Plural values (instrumental, relational, intrinsic via criteria)	Intrinsic value (nature as rights-bearing entity)
Instrumental value: use vs non-use?	Use only (non-use invisible)	Use + non-use (non-use marginal)	Use + non-use (if monetisable)	Use + indirect use (non-use weakly operationalised)	Use framed as loss-gain units	Use (service-based)	Use + non-use but includes moral concerns beyond those values	Rejects use/non-use framing
Representation?	Implicit prices (observed behaviour)	Monetary (single metric; welfare aggregation)	Monetary (constructed preferences; survey-based)	Biophysical + monetary (standardised accounts)	Standardised, tradable units (verified outcomes)	Quantified service indicators (performance-based)	Multiple (indicators, scores, deliberation)	Legal-normative (rights, duties, guardianship)
Commensurability?	Implicit (within market domains)	Required (full commensurability)	Strongly assumed (monetary comparability)	Assumed (via standardised indicators/accounts)	Required (for trading/exchange)	Partial (within programme scope)	Conditional (via scoring and weighting)	Rejected (non-commensurable)
Implied human-nature ontology?	Nature as amenity / production factor	Nature as resource for human welfare	Nature as object of human preference	Nature as capital base of economy	Nature as exchangeable outcomes	Nature as service provider	Nature as relational partner (but operationalised)	Nature as rights-bearing subject
Comparison / aggregation?	Econometric aggregation	Welfare optimisation (cost-benefit)	Statistical aggregation	Aggregation via accounts/indices	Market exchange & offset ratios	Programme-level aggregation	Deliberative weighting + scoring	Juridical reasoning, thresholds
Outside the scope?	Non-use, intrinsic, relational values — not observable in behaviour	Intrinsic, relational values — excluded by monetisation	Non-monetisable, relational values — limited to expressed preferences	Relational, lived, Indigenous values — excluded by aggregation	Intrinsic, relational, unique values — excluded by standardisation	Intrinsic, relational values — excluded by contractual service logic	Non-tradable values (e.g. sacred, moral) — reduced to trade-offs	Efficiency and trade-offs — excluded by rights-based logic
Non-monetisable values?	Excluded	Marginalised or monetised	Monetised or excluded	Acknowledged, not operationalised	Rarely captured	Weakly included (e.g. safeguards)	Included via criteria (imperfectly)	Foundational

Conclusion

This report provides an ethical reflection on the most commonly used nature valuation instruments in the EU and beyond, and in particular assesses how these instruments capture different values of nature. While acknowledging the limitations of the tripartite value typology—instrumental, intrinsic, and relational values of nature—as discussed in the relevant ethical literature in the section on the analytical framework, it nonetheless builds on these three value types, given their centrality in environmental policy-related literature.

In the European policy context, the valuation of nature is not driven by the use of a single preferred instrument; different instruments cover different phases of the policy process and policy domains. No single instrument captures the full range of values associated with nature (e.g., instrumental, relational, intrinsic). Each instrument rests on different assumptions about what nature is, how it matters, and how decisions should be made. Valuation instruments thus do not represent neutral technical tools: they embed particular understandings of how nature is valued and of human–nature relationships. Whether nature is treated as capital, a service provider, a partner, or a rights-holder depends on the chosen framework — and this choice may shape policy outcomes.

The most commonly used instruments — particularly economic and market-based approaches such as CBA, stated- and revealed-preference methods, PES, and nature and biodiversity credits — prioritise instrumental values. They assess nature primarily in quantitative terms, measuring its contribution to human welfare, economic activity, or ecosystem services. While these dominant approaches are effective in making environmental impacts visible within political and economic systems, they tend to overlook intrinsic and relational values of nature. This creates a structural tension between policies that require

commensurable, comparable metrics and ethical perspectives that emphasise incommensurability, non-substitutability, and moral limits to trade-offs.

A key reason for this is that even when broader values are acknowledged in principle, decision-making systems frequently privilege what can be quantified, priced, or traded. This reinforces a logic in which environmental losses and gains are commensurable and harm in one place can be offset by improvement elsewhere. The use of nature and biodiversity credits as well as PES, for example, widely illustrates outcome-based and incentive-driven governance: these instruments can mobilise funding and integrate nature into economic decision-making but may also simplify complex ecological relationships and may legitimise continued environmental harm through offsetting.

As a response to these limitations, plural and intrinsic approaches are gaining not only discursive but also practical prominence, while remaining less institutionalised. Although internationally there is an increase in RoN becoming part of national constitutions, in the European context it remains marginal in practice, as it is not formally adopted at the EU level. The RoN framework represents a departure from conventional valuation instruments by recognising nature as a rights-bearing entity rather than a resource or asset. As such, RoN reframes governance by foregrounding legal recognition of nature as a rights-bearing entity rather than treating economic valuation as the primary basis for decision-making. Although still emerging in policy practice, this framework offers a complementary pathway for integrating intrinsic value into decision-making.

A further visible trend within environmental policy and valuation approaches is the growing emphasis on system-level thinking. NCA and nature and biodiversity credit systems aim to integrate ecosystems and biodiversity into macroeconomic frameworks. This enhances their visibility in economic systems, though it continues to frame nature primarily as productive infrastructure and thus reinforces instrumental perspectives on the value of nature. Furthermore, MCA adopts a more systematic approach, allowing for a broader range of ecological, social, and cultural considerations to inform decisions, especially through participatory processes. However, MCA still operates within trade-off-based decision-making logics.

The approaches explored herein are, when applied individually, seen to be insufficient to deliver effective environmental policy outcomes across policy contexts. In practice, the combination of different instruments may help align plural value perspectives with the operational requirements of policymaking. However, combining instruments does not necessarily resolve underlying ethical conflicts, as the dominant decision-making logics — particularly those based on trade-offs and aggregation — may continue to shape outcomes. Only through the balanced use of complementary instruments, policymakers may avoid marginalising relational or intrinsic values of nature.

Finally, across instruments, valuation instruments tend to perform differently depending on methodological choice and the governance practices within which they are embedded. The iterative development of instruments, e.g., through piloting, sensitivity testing, and revision, may render unintended effects such as problematic incentives, distributional impacts, or ecological oversimplification (which are not always apparent at the design stage) visible. The credibility and policy influence of valuation results are also shaped by factors such as the quality of underlying data; transparency about assumptions and uncertainty; and institutional arrangements for oversight, participation, and review.

Annex 1: Valuation instruments

Cost-benefit analysis (CBA)

Value of nature

CBA evaluates changes in aggregate human welfare resulting from impacts on nature. In its conventional form, CBA is fundamentally anthropocentric: nature is valued instrumentally, only insofar as it affects human well-being, rather than as having independent moral standing. The intrinsic value of nature as well as relational values, such as cultural, spiritual, or identity-based connections to nature, are typically not adequately captured within monetary valuation frameworks. As Fuggitt and Wilcox (1999) note, standard CBA only recognises humans as holders of value. Baum (2012, p. 501), however, argues that nature could, in principle, be valued intrinsically within CBA — but only if the method were expanded beyond its conventional form into a broader “intrinsic value-based CBA.”

In theory, CBA can incorporate both use and non-use values of nature, such as existence or bequest values. In practice, however, non-use values are often weakly represented and tend to be marginalised in assessments. More broadly, CBA relies on a single monetary metric to represent value, rendering diverse environmental, social, and economic impacts quantitative and commensurable. This implies that different types of impacts can be compared, traded off, and substituted for one another through their monetary equivalents. As a result, losses in one domain can, in principle, be compensated by gains in another.

Similarly, Anderson (1993) argues that reducing all value to a single metric distorts plural value structures.

The economic conception of sustainability that underpins much conventional CBA is commonly described as “weak sustainability” (Atkinson et al., 2018, pp. 290–294), which assumes that natural capital, at least to some extent, is substitutable with other forms of capital, provided that total wealth is maintained over time. Weak sustainability is distinguished from conceptions of strong sustainability that rest on the idea that certain forms of natural capital are non-substitutable or “critical” and should not be degraded. This poses a challenge to conventional CBA because it introduces limits or thresholds that cannot be traded off against economic benefits. A key practical manifestation of this perspective is biodiversity offsetting, whereby projects that damage ecosystems are required to finance compensating environmental improvements elsewhere. Strong sustainability pays attention to irreversibility, implying more cautious decision-making when ecosystem losses could be irreversible (Atkinson et al., 2018).

Finally, the literature acknowledges significant constraints in applying CBA to environmental decision-making, particularly the difficulty of quantifying certain benefits while maintaining methodological rigour (Independent Evaluation Group, 2010). To address this, the OECD recommends setting a clear analytical scope and monetising impacts wherever possible, to allow consistent comparison of benefits and costs across multiple dimensions (Byström, Dussaux, and Hassett, 2025).

Case studies

Cost–benefit analysis has become an established tool across a range of environment-related policy domains throughout the EU, where it is used to inform investment and regulatory decisions. In the context of the EU, well-known examples of CBA in practice comprise the European Investment Bank (EIB), which adopts CBA as its standard approach for estimating a project’s economic rate of return (ERR), capturing not only financial outcomes but also wider social benefits and costs, including environmental externalities (European Commission, 2021a, p. 11).

Climate change mitigation is assessed using the methodology set out in the 2014 EC Guide to cost–benefit analysis of investment projects (European Commission Directorate-General for Regional and Urban Policy, 2015), which estimates a project’s net greenhouse gas emissions or savings relative to a baseline using appropriate emission factors and then monetises the resulting tonnes of CO₂ equivalent through an applied shadow price of carbon expressed in euros per tonne.

Furthermore, CBA is commonly applied in areas such as renewable energy and energy efficiency; municipal waste management, transport, water, and wastewater (for example, in Romania; Platon, Antonescu and Constantinescu, 2015); territorial and urban development; or the remediation of polluted areas (for example, in Slovakia; Institute of Environmental Politics, 2019). In the building sector, it informs assessments of projects with environmental implications, such as in identifying possible ways to decarbonise the EU building sector in a cost-effective manner, e.g., through energy renovations and calculating cost-optimal levels of minimum energy performance requirements for buildings (for example, in Germany and Greece; Filippidou and Jimenez Navarro, 2019).

Other case studies documented by the OECD comprise speed limit reduction (carbon emissions, local air pollutants and noise, time losses, etc.), the phasedown of production and consumption of hydrofluorocarbons, or conversion premiums for private vehicles (Byström et al., 2025).

Use / developments / recommendations

Within the European Union, CBA is formally embedded in the Better Regulation Impact Assessment framework (European Commission, 2023), while internationally it is reflected in guidance such as that of the OECD (Atkinson et al., 2018) and the World Bank as well as the UK Treasury’s “Green Book” (HM Treasury, 2013). In recent years, CBA has also become closely linked to “green budgeting.” Under the EU’s broad definition, green budgeting involves using budgetary tools — including environmental valuation instruments such as impact assessments and environmental CBA — to better align public budgets with the Union’s climate and environmental goals. CBA is commonly used in environmental impact assessments (European Commission, 2021b).

CBA alone is often described as insufficient as a stand-alone valuation instrument. Oftentimes, it is recommended to use MCA and other instruments to complement CBA (European Commission, 2021a, p. 26). For instance, in the *Guidelines for implementing an Ecosystem-based Approach in Maritime Spatial Planning* (European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency, 2021), CBA is explicitly mentioned as part of the toolkit which also includes MCA. The OECD notes that while cost–benefit analysis provides useful information for decision-makers, it is only one part of the broader set of considerations involved in complex environmental decisions (Atkinson et al., 2018). How CBA is applied in practice, and the limits and challenges of its use, are crucial for understanding both its benefits and its potential misuse. Decision-makers need flexibility to pursue political or other policy objectives, but this often influences how CBA is used. CBA’s role in this process may

therefore be limited to illustrating the economic implications of alternative choices rather than prescribing which option should be chosen.

Furthermore, the OECD has provided an overview of developments in the theory and practice of CBA, with increasing attention devoted to assessing the social costs of carbon as a major one (Atkinson et al., 2018, p. 3). This reflects efforts to better capture long-term and global climate impacts within economic appraisal but may not remove the need to complement CBA with other approaches when dealing with deep uncertainty, thresholds, or non-substitutable environmental losses.

Multi-criteria analysis (MCA)

Value of nature

MCA is widely used to identify options that perform well across multiple criteria relevant to nature and society, particularly in contested situations where trade-offs arise, such as between biodiversity conservation and land use. It may be suited to decision-making contexts in which monetary and non-monetary values coexist, as it enables the inclusion of instrumental, relational, and intrinsic dimensions of nature in both qualitative and quantitative form. MCA typically captures impacts that can be expressed as decision criteria, including ecological condition, ecosystem services, socio-economic effects, cultural or landscape values, and aspects of risk or resilience. These are represented through biophysical indicators, expert judgement, or stakeholder preference ratings and are combined to evaluate alternatives in a systematic and transparent way (French et al., 2009).

In practice, the valuation of nature in MCA occurs through the selection of criteria; the design of indicators; and subsequent processes of scoring, weighting, and aggregation. Non-monetisable considerations are incorporated

through scoring systems, deliberative weighting, or proxy indicators that render them comparable to biophysical or economic criteria. In this way, MCA functions not only as an assessment tool but also as a structuring device that shapes how nature is represented in decision-making.

At the same time, MCA tends to struggle with values that cannot be meaningfully expressed as discrete decision criteria to be scored and traded off, such as sacred meanings or moral duties toward nature, systemic ecological uncertainty, long-term or irreversible harms, or non-anthropocentric claims that reject trade-offs altogether. For example, treating a sacred site or a protected species as a criterion to be partially “offset” or outweighed by economic benefits changes the claim from “this should not be harmed” into “how much harm is acceptable.” Although MCA is often presented as pluralistic, it relies on implicit logics of comparability, trade-off permissibility, decision orientation, and stakeholder representability. This can privilege articulable values, favour impacts that can be stabilised into criteria, and translate ethical conflicts into questions of weighting. For these reasons, MCA has increasingly been used for nature conservation (Adem Esmail & Geneletti, 2018).

Case studies

Cases of use of MCA in nature-related domains are broad, including forest management and restoration (e.g., Prokofieva et al., 2011); conservation prioritisation and planning; protected area planning and management; and mapping of biodiversity, wilderness, and naturalness (Adem Esmail & Geneletti, 2018).

The EU Joint Research Centre (JRC) has developed a specific software tool that supports MCA applications for ex-ante impact assessment problems, i.e. SOCRATES (SOcial multi CRiteria AssessmenT of European policieS). This tool has been employed in several impact assessments, including for the *Regulation (EU) 2024/1938* on standards of quality and safety for substances of human origin

intended for human application, the UN International Atomic Energy Agency's activities in decommissioning and environmental remediation, and EU regulations on eco-design requirements for local space heaters (OECD, 2025a). Another tool funded by the EU, widely used in the mobility sector, is MAMCA (Multi-Actor Multi-Criteria Analysis; MAMCA.eu, n.d.). Other countries have also developed their own MCA tools (e.g., the UK; OECD, 2009).

EU case studies comprise applications in the energy space (OECD, 2025a) as well as airport expansion assessments in Europe and beyond (International Transport Forum, 2017). Oftentimes, decision-makers employ both MCA and CBA (cost-benefit analysis) in tandem to address problems, e.g., in understanding and applying the precautionary principle in the energy transition (OECD, 2023) and in policy related to single-use plastics (World Bank, 2025). Scholarship discusses a wider range of domains where MCA could further serve as a relevant tool in the EU environmental policy context, such as considering sea level rise adaptation measures (Galluccio et al., 2024) and in evaluating regional bioeconomy potential in European countries (Kalimeris et al., 2025).

Beyond the EU, cases include suggested use by the OECD (2024a) in the infrastructure context, the use of in hydropower in Bhutan (World Bank Group, 2016), and the use in river-basin governance in the Campoalegre River Basin in Colombia (Gonzalez et al., 2024). The IPBES also explicitly works with MCA assessments to acknowledge the diversity of values and valuations of nature (Pascual et al., 2017).

Use / developments / recommendations

MCDA is especially valuable when it is impractical or undesirable to simplify a multi-objective problem into a single objective, particularly in participatory contexts where diverse stakeholders pursue different goals (Linkov et al., 2006).

In international contexts, MCA and CBA are often used simultaneously to serve different purposes. While CBA provides a standard framework producing quantitative estimates that can be used to compare and rank projects, MCA can accommodate a broader range of objectives, including longer-term environmental sustainability goals; MCA is, however, less widely used in many appraisal contexts (OECD, 2025b, p. 142). Scholarship has advocated for combining MCA and CBA valuation methods, suggesting that multi-criteria cost-benefit analysis (MCCBA) offers a strong foundation for assessing projects or policies that affect agricultural and natural ecosystem services (Sijtsma et al., 2013).

Natural capital accounting (NCA)

Value of nature

NCA represents nature through accounts that describe stocks and flows of natural capital, typically at aggregated spatial or sectoral levels rather than at the level of individual sites or practices. It creates systematically compiled information that can be integrated into models linking environmental change with economic outcomes (Bagstad et al., 2021). Ecosystems are thus treated as productive infrastructure “underpin[ning] [...] economic prosperity and well-being” (European Union Research and Innovation, 2019, p. 2) and making visible “the contributions of nature to the economy and people” (United Nations Statistical Commission, 2021, p. 2).

The value logic inherent in NCA is predominantly instrumental, focusing on use and indirect use values aggregated at macro- or sectoral scales. Non-use values, intrinsic values, and relational values are weakly operationalised and generally enter only indirectly. As Hein et al. (2020) note, natural capital accounts have limited capacity to reflect ecosystem complexity, including, for example,

resilience, thresholds, and the risk of sudden collapse. It is data- and capacity-intensive and remains uneven in coverage, especially for biodiversity and ecosystem conditions.

Value is represented through a combination of biophysical indicators (e.g., hectares, tonnes, condition indices) and monetary accounts. NCA does not require monetary valuation to function; many accounts are purely physical, i.e., tracking the extent, condition, and change of ecosystems over time without assigning prices (European Union, 2021a). To remain consistent with national economic accounts, monetary values in NCA are based on market-compatible monetary measures rather than estimates of nature's broader worth to society. As a result, monetary ecosystem values are inherently limited in scope.

Furthermore, while NCA appears technically objective, it relies on prior choices about how ecosystems are classified, which thresholds are applied, and which indicators are selected; these choices are shaped, among other factors, by national policy priorities and institutional and governance contexts.

Case studies

The UN SEEA represents the most established international framework for NCA. It links ecosystem extent, condition, and ecosystem services to economic activity. SEEA distinguishes between ecosystem extent and condition accounts, ecosystem services accounts (covering supply, use and beneficiaries), and, where appropriate, monetary asset accounts (World Bank, 2023, p. 9). The framework has been implemented through multiple initiatives. The NCAVES project piloted SEEA Ecosystem Accounting (SEEA-EA) across five countries (Brazil, China, India, Mexico, and South Africa) and demonstrated that SEEA functions as a flexible accounting framework rather than a fixed valuation method, notably by enabling adaptation of global Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) indicator methods to national circumstances and supporting the use of nationally relevant physical indicators (UNEP, n.d.). In the EU, NCA is

becoming institutionalised through the integration of SEEA-based ecosystem accounts into official statistics under *Regulation (EU) No 691/2011* (Bagstad et al., 2021) and the introduction of mandatory ecosystem accounts under *Regulation (EU) 2024/3024* (European Commission, n.d.). At the EU level, the integration of SEEA into official statistical frameworks builds directly on earlier experimental and pilot work under the Integrated system for Natural Capital Accounting (INCA), which served as a testbed for applying SEEA Ecosystem Accounting in the EU (European Union Research and Innovation, 2019). INCA operationalises SEEA-EA using a tiered approach to ecosystem extent, condition, and services, drawing on the EU initiative on Mapping and Assessment of Ecosystems and Services (MAES; La Notte et al., 2022). At the global level, the World Bank-backed WAVES programme supports countries in integrating SEEA-based accounts into national planning and finance ministries (Bass et al., 2017).

Across these initiatives, SEEA-based accounts have supported SDG reporting, indicator development, and policy analysis; enabled cross-sectoral dialogue by providing a shared statistical language; and made visible the economic relevance of ecosystems without requiring monetisation. INCA applications, for example, have shown that losses of semi-natural ecosystems were lower inside Natura 2000 areas than outside, identified households as the main beneficiaries of ecosystem services, and estimated ecosystem service values of around €62 billion in 2012, supporting the case for public investment in ecosystem assets (European Union Research and Innovation, 2019).

At the same time, several limitations are inherent to SEEA-based NCA. While SEEA supports comparability and policy relevance, it necessarily involves normative decisions about boundaries, classifications, and indicators, reflecting specific epistemic frameworks rather than universal ways of relating to nature. Relational and lived dimensions of human–nature relationships largely fall outside the accounting structure and are addressed, where at all, through interpretation rather than formal accounts. As argued by Larson et al. (2025) and Normyle et al. (2022), SEEA-EA does not, by default, capture Indigenous

conceptualisations of nature or cultural connections to land and requires increased consultation and co-design to do so. Across NCA initiatives, data gaps, particularly at relevant spatial and temporal scales, have been identified as a persistent constraint (Bagstad et al., 2021), which may raise concerns in cases where incomplete accounts shape valuation and policy priorities; effective implementation has been shown to rely on collaboration between statistical and scientific bodies, together with close engagement with end users, so that accounts and indicators are shaped by — and responsive to — policy and decision-making needs.

At the national level, in New Zealand, a Treasury-commissioned synthesis (Clough, Bealing & Goodall, 2017) found that existing natural capital estimates are fragmented, often retrospective, and rarely applied in a consistent way to assess long-term sustainability or future risk.

Use / developments / recommendations

NCA is also increasingly relevant for EU sustainable finance and corporate governance frameworks. SEEA-based natural capital accounts are expected to form part of the evidence base for the *EU Taxonomy for Sustainable Activities* over time, particularly for objectives relating to the protection and restoration of biodiversity and ecosystems (National Economic & Social Development Office, 2024, p. 28). NCA also underpins emerging corporate reporting and risk-assessment practices, e.g., under the *Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive* (CSRD — 2022/2464; via double materiality and European Sustainability Reporting Standards – ESRS – standards that explicitly cover biodiversity, water and resource use; Amicarelli et al., 2025) — and may support broader disclosure requirements under sustainable finance transparency initiatives such as the *Sustainable Finance Disclosure Regulation* (SFDR; e.g., Dinesen, 2025).

Revealed-preference methods (hedonic pricing / travel cost)

Value of nature

Revealed-preference methods capture instrumental use values. Non-use, intrinsic, or purely moral values are structurally invisible when revealed-preference methods are used exclusively in valuation.

When using revealed-preference methods, nature is framed as a factor affecting market choices. In hedonic methods, for example, environmental quality (such as clean air or proximity to green space) is treated as one attribute among others in a composite good — for example, a house — and its value is inferred from how much prices vary with that characteristic. In the travel cost method, nature is valued through the expenses people incur to access a recreational site; these expenditures function as a proxy for the value of the recreational experience (Boyle, 2003). In both cases, environmental goods enter appraisal only insofar as they shape observable market-related decisions. Values that do not translate into such behaviour remain outside the scope of the method.

Value is represented quantitatively through implicit prices derived econometrically. In hedonic models, statistical techniques are used “to isolate the implicit ‘price’ of environmental characteristics from observed market data (Atkinson, 2010, p. 14). In travel cost applications, value is inferred from how much people spend to access a recreational site and how visitation responds to changes in travel costs (Atkinson, 2010, p. 195). In both cases, environmental benefits are translated into quantitative estimates of the overall benefits people derive based on actual choices and then aggregated to estimate overall welfare effects at the population level.

Commensurability is assumed implicitly within the relevant market domain: environmental quality is rendered comparable to other goods through its effect on prices or travel expenditures. However, this comparability is limited to contexts where behaviour can be observed and modelled. As the *Better Regulation Toolbox* notes, while revealed-preference methods are “perceived to be more reliable” than stated-preference methods (as they are based on observed behaviour in real markets rather than hypothetical choices), the environmental good being valued must already exist in some form and already influence behaviour (European Commission, 2023, p. 519). Furthermore, because values are inferred from actual expenditures, results are also shaped by access and existing inequalities: only those who participate in housing or recreation markets, for example, reveal preferences. Benefits that do not generate observable behaviour, such as existence or bequest values, remain outside the valuation result.

Case studies

Many widely cited applications of revealed-preference methods take the form of empirical studies commissioned to inform policy debates rather than instruments routinely embedded in formal policy appraisal. Within the EU, the travel cost method has been used to estimate the recreational benefits of protected areas, including in studies of Natura 2000 sites. A study by BIO Intelligence Service (2011, p. 45) uses travel costs to estimate welfare benefits from visits to Natura 2000 areas and to differentiate benefits across user groups (e.g. walkers), thereby rendering recreational ecosystem services visible as use values grounded in observed expenditure. Internationally, hedonic pricing has been applied to air pollution in Jakarta, Indonesia, where Yusuf and Resosudarmo (2009) infer the value residents place on clean air from spatial variation in housing rents and prices.

Use / developments / recommendations

Revealed-preference methods are primarily used where policy appraisal requires monetised estimates grounded in observed behaviour. Their perceived robustness in the policy context may reflect the methods’ reliance on real-world choices rather than hypothetical preferences (European Commission, 2023). At the same time, their applicability is constrained by the need for existing markets and observable behaviour, making them unsuitable for valuing non-use, intrinsic, or relational dimensions of nature. Because estimates reflect who participates in relevant markets, they may under-represent benefits accruing to excluded or future populations.

Stated-preference methods (contingent valuation / choice experiments)

Value of nature

In valuation terms, stated-preference methods value expressed preferences for specified policy changes rather than for ecosystems as such: the object is the described change scenario as respondents understand it (e.g., improved water quality, reduced biodiversity loss, avoided spill risk), which makes resulting values sensitive to how scenarios are framed and perceived. Because respondents can express concern for the existence or bequest of nature, among others, some non-use considerations may be brought into view that would otherwise be hard to capture; however, stated-preference methods remain centred on what people are willing and able to articulate, given the information provided and the context in which the survey is conducted (the OECD, for example, notes that “most people are unfamiliar with placing monetary values on environmental goods”; Watson, 2021, p. 16).

In stated-preference methods, value is ultimately expressed in monetary terms (WTP or WTA), whether elicited directly (in the case of contingent valuation) or inferred from choices (in the case of choice experiments). This allows otherwise diverse effects to be compared within the appraisal, even when uncertainty is acknowledged (for example, the Toolbox notes that it “may be difficult to judge the reliability” of a single estimate and recommends ranges and sensitivity; European Commission, 2023, p. 519). Environmental goods enter evaluation to the extent that they are translated into changes that people perceive as relevant and can evaluate in a “constructed or hypothetical market” (Atkinson, 2010, p. 14). Responses from a sample of people are used to infer what the wider population might value (e.g., mean or median WTP); results are thus strongly linked to sampling, representativeness, and modelling choices (European Commission, 2023).

What tends to fall outside scope of contingent valuation are values people cannot or will not monetise (for example, a belief that something “should not be traded” or “should be free”) as well as distributional or power effects that shape whose preferences are expressed and how (e.g., response bias and sample representativeness — Hassett et al., 2025, p. 14 — or social desirability — i.e., responding to “what is socially expected” — Scarpa, 2012, p. 6), which the monetary outputs do not by themselves resolve. Non-monetisable values are therefore either translated into money terms (with uncertainty acknowledged) or handled outside the valuation result via complementary (e.g., qualitative) assessment.

Case studies

A canonical example of CV in practice is the Exxon Valdez oil spill valuation. After the 1989 spill in Prince William Sound in the US state of Alaska, authorities sought to assess not only clean-up costs and market losses but also the non-use values lost by the wider public. This included values like existence and bequest.

For example, “the majority of Americans had never visited Prince William Sound, but still may have derived value from knowing that the public resource was protected” (National Ocean Economics Program, 2015). A large-scale CV study was therefore commissioned to estimate the public’s willingness to pay to avoid comparable environmental damage. The resulting estimate (around USD 2.8 billion; National Ocean Economics Program, 2015) made explicit that environmental harm extends beyond use-based benefits and that such non-use values can be significant even when they are not tied to direct experience or economic activity. The case illustrates the extensive use of focus groups and pilot testing to ensure comprehension and legitimacy. In addition, valuation was viewed not only as an abstract pricing exercise — treating monetary estimates as stand-alone measures of environmental worth — but, as determined by U.S. court rulings and the *Oil Pollution Act of 1990* (National Ocean Economics Program, 2015), also as a legally mandated tool for assigning responsibility. At the same time, this case highlights ethical limits inherent in CV. The presence of “protest votes” (e.g., Johnson, 2006), where respondents refuse to state a WTP because they believe polluters should pay or that losses should not be traded for money, signals moral concerns that cannot be resolved within the valuation itself. Losses were framed as “lost non-use values ... to the American public” (National Ocean Economics Program, 2015), meaning that values entered the analysis only insofar as they could be expressed as human preferences; this leaves questions of intrinsic worth and moral limits outside the valuation process.

Within the EU, a JRC-led choice experiment (La Notte et al., 2021) estimated the non-use value of biodiversity protection. The study was conducted in four EU Member States (Czechia, Germany, Ireland, and Italy) and elicited citizens’ willingness to pay for habitat and species maintenance. As CV is highly sensitive to how the object of valuation is described, the study aimed at translating ecological processes into accessible concepts such as land-use change, agricultural practices, and the food chain, supported by focus groups and pilot

testing. For example, it quantified a non-use value that can be represented by the habitat and species maintenance service, so-called “glue value” rather than as a bundle of individual ecosystem services. Although the valuation remained dependent on how respondents understood and monetised the scenario, this approach limits one of the core ethical weaknesses of CV, i.e., the tendency to fragment nature into tradeable services that respondents struggle to understand or meaningfully compare. The resulting estimates, which were aggregated and spatially extrapolated to the EU level, suggest that Europeans would be willing to pay more than €30 billion annually for biodiversity protection, exceeding the €20 billion per year budget envisaged under the EU *Biodiversity Strategy for 2030*.

Use / developments / recommendations

Stated-preference methods are used to fill valuation gaps in appraisal: they monetise non-market impacts (biodiversity, air quality, landscape, risk reduction) so that these can be integrated into CBA and impact assessment. They are increasingly embedded in policy appraisal practice: the EU Better Regulation Toolbox treats stated-preference as part of the standard toolkit for monetising non-market impacts in CBA and impact assessment (European Commission, 2023, p. 519), while internationally, the OECD’s EPIC survey shows stated-preference diffusion into multi-sector household policy analysis across nine OECD countries (energy, transport, waste, and food; Hassett et al., 2025).

Analysis and case studies show that stated-preference methods can make non-use values visible and relevant for policy, provided scenarios are carefully framed and tested to ensure understanding and credibility. They should, however, therefore be used alongside complementary (e.g., qualitative) assessment rather than as stand-alone measures of nature’s value.

Payments for Ecosystem Services (PES)

Value of nature

PES schemes value the delivery or maintenance of specified ecosystem services. PES consists of arrangements by which “the beneficiaries of ecosystem services compensate those providing the services” (Cavelier and Munro Gray, 2012, p. 2). What is rewarded is therefore the provision of defined, performance-oriented services, e.g., carbon sequestration, water regulation, or biodiversity protection, that generate identifiable benefits for beneficiaries. Stewardship is recognised in contractual terms: land managers, for example, undertake prescribed actions because these are expected to deliver the targeted services. PES is thus grounded primarily in use-related instrumental values. Even where the benefits of PES are described as accruing more broadly (for example, when costs are incurred locally but benefits accrue globally, e.g. Adjognon, van Soest, and Guthoff, 2019, p. 1, such as in the case of global climate benefits from local carbon sequestration), these remain dispersed use values rather than intrinsic or relational values of nature. Stålhammar and Thorén (2019) argue that ecosystem services frameworks are structurally limited to instrumental, preference-based values and that relational values require a fundamentally different epistemological approach — one oriented toward the meanings people derive from relationships with nature rather than toward preference satisfaction.

Value in PES is represented monetarily through payments conditional on compliance with agreed practices, typically based on standardised rules within a scheme, and usually relying on short-term contracts. In practice, payments are often linked to actions rather than to verified ecological outcomes (Canessa, 2026). This reflects an assumption of limited commensurability: different actions can be compared and paid for within a programme, but without claiming ecological equivalence across ecosystems or services. Ecosystems are

framed as functional providers of benefits to humans, and this is consistent with a beneficiary-pays logic. Values that cannot be specified as services, such as long-term ecosystem integrity, interconnected ecological processes, or intrinsic value (Power, Dunz, and Gavryliuk, 2022), are addressed, if at all, indirectly through safeguards, eligibility rules, or complementary regulation rather than through the payment mechanism itself (OECD, 2024b, p. 11).

Case studies

Costa Rica's national PES programme has been cited as the most established national example of PES in practice (Porrás & Chacón-Cascante, 2018, p. 2). The programme compensates landowners for activities "identified as contributing to a sustainable environment, including conservation of natural forests, reforestation through sustainable plantations and agro-forestry," with payments made in exchange for ecosystem services such as forest protection, carbon sequestration, water regulation, and biodiversity conservation (Cavelier and Munro Gray, 2012, p. 6). A key strength of the programme lies in its legal embedding: the *Forestry Law* formally recognises ecosystem services; secures stable public funding; and mandates a single public intermediary to manage contracts, monitoring, and transparency (Hinojosa, 2017). The programme has served over 18k families and 100k Indigenous people (UNFCCC, n.d.). At the same time, evidence is limited in reductions to deforestation rates (Porrás and Chacón-Cascante, 2018, p. 8). However, the programme exemplifies the instrumental logic of PES: nature is valued primarily as a service provider, stewardship is framed in performance-oriented contractual terms, and value is represented through cash payments linked to five-year contracts and compliance with management plans rather than to verified ecological outcomes. Non-monetisable values are partly addressed through regulatory safeguards (e.g. prohibitions on cutting primary forest; Porrás and Chacón-Cascante, 2018, p. 2).

REDD+ (Reducing Emissions from Deforestation and Forest Degradation) is an international climate mechanism, backed by the United Nations, that provides results-based finance to developing countries for reducing forest-related carbon emissions, often being implemented at the national level through PES-type incentive schemes. Within this framework (see ICIMOD, 2017), REDD+ emphasises long-term institutionalisation rather than short-term projects, which is reflected in national REDD strategies, permanent monitoring systems, and repeated payment cycles tied to continued performance. The mechanism requires monitoring and reporting as well as transparent baselines, thereby limiting arbitrary valuation and strengthening accountability for claimed outcomes. REDD+ also links international payments to national funds and, in some cases, to local PES mechanisms, embedding incentives within existing public institutions rather than relying solely on markets. REDD+ has made the need for social and environmental safeguards explicit to "avoid perverse incentives" (ICIMOD, 2017, p. 2). At the same time, REDD+ largely values forests through a single, commensurable carbon metric.

CAP eco-schemes are an annual, voluntary instrument under the EU's *Common Agricultural Policy* (CAP 2023-2027) that reward farmers for adopting practices that go beyond baseline conditionality and are "beneficial for the climate, the environment and animal welfare" (EU CAP Network, 2023, p. 3). Value is represented monetarily through payments that typically compensate for "additional costs incurred and income foregone" (EU CAP Network, 2023, p. 5). The eco-schemes' main strength lies in mainstreaming environmental responsibility into agricultural income support at scale, with Member States required to allocate at least 25% of direct payments to them (EU CAP Network, 2023, p. 2) — this embeds environmental action within routine agricultural governance. At the same time, the EU CAP Network (2023, p. 10) notes that eco-schemes are "not sufficiently adapted to regional or local situations" which enable situated ecological decision-making.

Use / developments / recommendations

The traditional focus of PES is on conservation; however, initiatives have expanded to water, biodiversity, and carbon (e.g., ICIMOD, 2017). Policy uptake is on the rise; for example, the OECD's Policy Instruments for the Environment (PINE) database shows 28 countries implementing 51 PES schemes in 2024 (OECD, 2024b, p. 5).

When using PES, intrinsic value, place-based relationships, and broader ecological and social meanings of forests remain only indirectly addressed through safeguards. Although PES schemes require mostly one-year commitments, environmental improvements require longer timeframes. Longer-term ecological integrity, place-based stewardship, and relational attachments to land may remain only partially recognised and may be constrained by short contractual timeframes. Lliso et al. (2021) argue that PES schemes must be tailored to their specific contexts, stating that practitioners can draw on local knowledge to design approaches that align with community cultures and worldviews, and that this is crucial, as PES can reshape intrinsic motivations and alter how people relate to their environment.

Nature and biodiversity credits

Value of nature

Within credit systems, nature or biodiversity is treated as a set of quantifiable, exchangeable outcomes. In policy documents, nature is illustrated as an asset that can attract capital and generate returns. In the EU Roadmap towards Nature Credits, for instance, nature credits are referred to as investments into "nature-positive actions" that generate ecological improvements and socio-economic co-benefits (European Commission, 2025a). And, according to the

World Bank Group (n.d., p. 4), a "global market for these credits has the potential to create a new source of private sector funding." These statements frame biodiversity value in terms of measurement, outcomes, and units rather than in terms of moral standing or relationships.

As nature in these credit schemes is primarily valued for the services it provides to economic actors (European Commission, 2025b), this reinforces an outcome- and benefit-oriented conception of value. Within policy documents, use-related instrumental values, including contributions to ecosystem resilience, risk reduction, business continuity, and reputational benefits, are dominant. For instance, nature credits are explicitly associated with reputational and legitimacy gains (European Commission, 2025b). Non-use values, e.g., bequest and existence, are present but remain implicit and operationalised instrumentally rather than articulated as ethical commitments. This instrumental view is visible in how conservation is treated. Conservation appears as a recognised objective but is framed as a creditable outcome: protection of biodiversity, for example, is treated within policy documents as something that can be purchased voluntarily (Markandya, 2022), banked as a "beneficial outcome [...] beyond business as usual" (OECD, 2012, p. 181), and later used within offsetting or compensation schemes. Similarly, future-oriented language referring to permanence invokes bequest values; however, this is done without explicit ethical framing. References to guaranteeing increases in biodiversity over time ("Protection [...] guarantees an increase in its biodiversity level over time"; Markandya, 2022, p. 23) may point to intergenerational concern; existence value is, however, not named as such and remains secondary to outcome delivery and market-oriented logic.

The valuation logic surrounding nature credits primarily speaks to loss-gain accounting. For example, as described in a World Bank report, a developer who causes biodiversity loss in one location may acquire an equivalent gain elsewhere to achieve "no net loss" (Markandya, 2022, p. 24). In the case of biodiversity credits, Wauchope et al. (2024) and Ducros and Steele (2022, in

Wunder et al., 2025) argue that what is valued is not nature per se but measured biodiversity performance translated into units, including both “biodiversity uplift” and “avoided biodiversity loss” relative to a baseline. These framings rely on baselines, or the state of nature at a defined starting point, and counterfactuals, or estimates of what would have occurred in the absence of the intervention. Nature’s value is thus realised through measurable change that can be accounted for and compensated rather than, for example, through explicit recognition of existence or intrinsic value. Furthermore, as credits operate within a mitigation or offset framework rather than being designed around absolute protection, they may permit continued environmental harm elsewhere. As reflected in the mitigation hierarchy, biodiversity offsets are defined as a “last resort mechanism” (UNEP, 2023a, p. 21), raising concerns that crediting schemes can legitimise ongoing degradation provided it is compensated.

Biodiversity and nature credit systems rely on measurable ecological indicators and verification protocols (Markandya, 2022). A “workable” biodiversity metric renders ecological outcomes comparable across sites, with value constructed, for example, through composite indicators such as species richness, the importance and intactness of flora and fauna, the International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN) risk status of ecosystems, and ecological connectivity (Markandya, 2022, p. 23). These indicators act as proxies for the state and quality of nature. However, this assumption of partial commensurability remains problematic: biodiversity is widely recognised as difficult to compare across locations and contexts (Wunder et al., 2025), and the lack of credible, standardised measurement approaches has been identified as a major challenge (European Business and Biodiversity Platform, 2025). As a result, trading across schemes is often impossible, as these schemes employ different metrics (Markandya, 2022). Schemes include the comprehensive aggregate model (using composite, direct measurements), the critical indicator model (based on higher-level, ecosystem-specific assessments), and the mosaic

compilation model (combining multiple types of measurements), alongside more than 35 methodologies that have emerged since the *Kunming–Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework* in December 2022 (World Economic Forum, 2024, p. 3).

Case studies

In the EU, discussions on this valuation instrument are emerging through the EU Roadmap towards Nature Credits (European Commission, 2025a), which outlines principles, governance considerations, and possible pathways for piloting and future development. Examples of use in the EU include restoring wetlands or extending forest areas (European Commission, 2025b). International examples include the Biodiversity Credit Alliance (2024) and the UK Biodiversity Net Gain system (UK Department for Environment, Food & Rural Affairs, 2023). The use of this instrument has been concentrated in OECD countries; for instance, New Zealand and Australia have taken steps to implement private sector markets for biodiversity credits (OECD, 2025c). However, beyond the OECD, Colombia applies biodiversity credits in public and private areas through performance-based schemes that support both regulatory and voluntary uses (Markandya, 2022, p. 23), and credits have been used in African countries in the form of wildlife credits to pay wildlife stewards for conservation efforts (e.g., Snyman, 2021).

Use / developments / recommendations

The literature on nature markets lists possible risks and constraints in their use. First, without strong governance, nature markets risk enabling greenwashing and delivering limited ecological benefits, as demonstrated by past failures in low-credibility carbon credit schemes (Trencher et al., 2024). Second, since biodiversity is a complex public good, i.e., those whose costs and quality are hard to specify and which are provided under constrained or non-competitive

market conditions, markets have inherent limits in conservation and may also produce unintended consequences such as reducing public funding and weakening collective environmental responsibility (Cinner et al., 2020). Third, redirecting subsidies that incentivise environmentally damaging practices in key sectors like agriculture, fisheries, and transport may be more effective in closing the finance gap than only deploying credit systems (WWF, 2024). Fourth, while additionality, i.e., the requirement that credits deliver benefits beyond existing or expected conservation outcomes, is widely treated as a key principle for nature credits, applying it too strictly could unfairly exclude long-standing conservation efforts and disadvantage those who already protect nature. And, finally, as nature markets grow, it is crucial to safeguard the rights and interests of local communities, as crediting schemes can reshape control over land, resources, and benefits in contexts where tenure and governance arrangements may be complex and contested (Fiore and Grabbe, 2025).

Bruegel's policy brief (Fiore and Grabbe, 2025) makes recommendations on how credit systems could be designed in the EU to support conservation and restoration while ensuring integrity, equity, and long-term ecological benefits. The think tank recommends consistent standards, lower transaction costs, clear rules for offsets, outcome-based metrics, mobilising demand through regulatory and financial incentives, maintaining public funding commitments, and the idea of "nature shares" as a complementary financial tool (see also Cantillon et al., 2025). In this approach, investors can purchase shares in large-scale conservation projects issued by jurisdictions (i.e., government authorities), thereby shifting incentives toward longer time horizons: investors become long-term stakeholders with a financial interest in the sustainability and permanence of the ecosystem rather than short-term buyers of one-off credits.

Rights of nature

Value of nature

Within the Rights of Nature (RoN) framework, nature is considered valuable in itself, with ecosystems and species valued independently of human use or preference. Nature is viewed as a moral subject, and this is reflected in granting it legal standing and, consequently, rights. This expresses the idea that the value of nature is not based solely on its instrumental or economic value to humans but also on its intrinsic value. In this sense, the RoN framework departs from valuation approaches that rely exclusively on use- or non-use-based framings of nature.

Case studies

Although most countries' constitutions include environmental provisions, the number of cases where nature is granted rights is limited but growing (e.g., OECD, 2022). The Kunming–Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework explicitly acknowledges the significance of the rights of nature. It states that, in countries where such rights are recognised, "the rights of nature and the rights of Mother Earth" form an essential component of the Framework's effective implementation (UNEP, 2022b, p. 5).

In the EU, there is only one case where nature has been granted rights, namely the case of the lagoon of Mar Menor in Spain (Government of Spain, 2022). It could also be argued that existing environmental policies, like the EU *Birds and Habitats Directives* (European Union, 2009), respect nature's intrinsic value by their embedded legal logic. At the same time, there are a considerable number of proposals in the European context aiming at recognising the rights of specific natural areas, with rivers, lakes, and seas featuring prominently. Notable examples include the Loire in France, the Meuse in the Netherlands, the Rhône

in Switzerland, and the Frome and Dart rivers in the United Kingdom (Haas, Burgers, and Putzer, 2025). Similar initiatives have also been advanced for other natural entities, such as Lake Vättern in Sweden, Rodden Meadow in the United Kingdom, and the North Sea (via the Embassy of the North Sea, a Netherlands-based organisation advocating for the North Sea to gain legal personhood by 2030; Haas, Burgers, and Putzer, 2023). Furthermore, Zoöp (n.d.) is a Dutch initiative that proposes a new governance model aiming at giving non-human entities a voice in organisational decision-making. The Confluence of European Water Bodies (n.d.) is a network of European water bodies for which activists are seeking to secure legal rights. The Global Alliance of the Rights of Nature (GARN Europe, n.d.) is a global network committed to the advocacy of RoN and working on a European Citizens' Initiative to have the rights of nature legally recognised at the EU level. Finally, and key to the spread of RoN cases in Europe, ecocide, grounded in the recognition that nature in itself is valuable and worth protecting, is recognised in many European countries' criminal laws, for example, in France and Belgium (Apelblat, 2025).

Outside the EU, the most well-known example of RoN is Ecuador's 2008 constitutional amendment, which formally recognised the rights of nature, making Ecuador the first country to enshrine such rights in its constitution (Charman, 2008). In 2010, Bolivia instituted the historic *Law of Mother Earth*, explicitly recognising Mother Earth not only as a sacred being but as a being with seven specific legal rights: the right to life, the diversity of life, to water and clean air, to maintenance of her components in a balanced way, to preservation from pollution, and to be restored (World Bank Group, 2019). In 2014, New Zealand's *Te Urewera Act* granted legal personhood to Te Urewera National Park and the Whanganui River, aligning with Māori values (New Zealand Government, 2014). In 2019, Uganda became the first nation in Africa to recognise RoN in national legislation, proclaiming the "nature has the right to exist, persist, maintain and regenerate its vital cycles, structure, functions and its processes in evolution" and that "a person has a right to bring an action

before a competent court for any infringement of rights of nature" (World Bank Group, 2020, p. 55). Other examples are found in Colombia, Australia, Canada, India, Bangladesh, the US, and Mexico (Kahui, Armstrong, and Aanesen, 2024).

Use / developments / recommendations

The recognition of RoN has been established through several constitutional, legislative, and judicial enactments, which aim to provide legal protection for non-human entities and natural systems. While, in theory, RoN functions as an effective nature conservation tool by enabling legal challenges to activities irrespective of their economic benefits, its limited institutionalisation to date has meant that it remains marginal in its effect on policy decisions.

Implementing a non-human rights-based framework in international and domestic law that gives nature a greater role in decision-making raises fundamental questions about responsibility for environmental harm such as climate change and biodiversity loss. Furthermore, embedding RoN in constitutional law alone has proven insufficient for meaningful environmental protection; to be truly effective, these rights must also be operationalised through criminal law by recognising and prosecuting ecocide.

Despite the growing number of initiatives, few have translated into binding legislation, partially due to the fact that many are advanced through advisory, local, or experimental arrangements that lack formal legal authority. While the number of RoN case studies worldwide is still relatively small — making it too early to determine whether they represent a departure from current governance structures in halting the decline of biodiversity — RoN has demonstrated the potential to contribute to this aim despite implementation challenges, such as in the case of the of the Los Cedros Forest in Ecuador (MOTH Life & TERRA Program, 2024).

A recently published edited volume, *Rights of Nature in Europe*, states that, given the diversity in interpretations and articulations of RoN, Europe fosters new

forms of interaction across distinct areas of law, knowledge, practices, and societal domains (García Ruales et al., 2024). Examples discussed in the volume include the dialogue between Indigenous worldviews and European legal systems, the interaction between environmental and human rights law in RoN litigation, the recognition of non-human voices in ecological decision-making, and the incorporation of RoN principles into professional fields such as eco-social work.

A comparative analysis of RoN case studies worldwide (Kahui, Armstrong, and Aanesen, 2024) shows that what many cases share is that they develop eco-centric approaches to governance alongside, and in contrast to, existing governance systems that may be seen as predominantly anthropocentric.

The analysis distinguishes between four types of cases. Those based on public guardianship — where the protection of nature relies on broad public standing (i.e., the ability of a wide range of actors to bring claims on nature's behalf) — and cases based on Environmental Legal Personhood (ELP), in which legal entities are established in relation to nature and represented by appointed

guardians. The latter category is further subdivided into indirect (where a legal entity is created to represent nature without recognising nature itself as a legal person), direct (where a specific natural entity, such as a river or ecosystem, is formally recognised as a legal person), and direct and living (where a specific natural entity is treated not only as a legal person but also as a living person, with harm treated analogously to harm to humans) forms, depending on the extent to which nature itself is formally recognised as a legal person.

Across RoN case studies, long-standing resistance by local, Indigenous, and environmental advocates to harmful development resulting from the failures of existing environmental governance led to the emergence of RoN. Indigenous philosophies have been central to this shift from a predominantly anthropocentric worldview to one that also recognises the intrinsic value of nature. While the language of purpose and value varies across cases, most (except indirect ELP models) reflect an eco-centric understanding of nature, which, in many cases, exists alongside, or remains in tension with, traditional approaches seen as anthropocentric (Kahui, Armstrong, and Aanesen, 2024).

Annex 2: Search strategy

Searches were conducted via Google using site-restricted queries limited to the domains of major EU and international public bodies (ec.europa.eu, oecd.org, worldbank.org, and un.org). Approximately three pages of results were screened per string. Document counts refer to materials extracted for further analysis.

Table 2. Search strings

Valuation instrument	Search strings used	Documents extracted (n)
Cost-benefit analysis	"cost-benefit analysis" AND (policy OR appraisal OR "impact assessment" OR evaluation) AND environment	11
Multi-criteria analysis	"multi-criteria analysis" AND (policy OR appraisal OR "impact assessment" OR evaluation) AND environment	15
Natural capital accounting	"natural capital accounting" AND (policy OR appraisal OR "impact assessment" OR evaluation) AND environment	20
Stated-preference methods	("stated preference" OR "contingent valuation" OR "choice experiment") AND (policy OR appraisal OR "impact assessment" OR evaluation) AND environment	17
Revealed-preference methods	("revealed preference" OR "hedonic pricing" OR "travel cost") AND (policy OR appraisal OR "impact assessment" OR evaluation) AND environment	10
Payments for ecosystem services	("payments for ecosystem services" OR "ecosystem service payments") AND (policy OR appraisal OR "impact assessment" OR evaluation) AND environment	23
Nature / biodiversity credits	("biodiversity credits" OR "nature credits") AND (policy OR appraisal OR "impact assessment" OR evaluation) AND environment	11
Rights of Nature	"rights of nature" AND (policy OR appraisal OR "impact assessment" OR evaluation) AND environment	10

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